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Article

Optimizing an Integrated Biorefining Process for Birch Veneer Chips and Lignocellulosic Residues: Enhancing Cellulose Preservation and Maximizing Furfural and Acetic Acid Production

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Abstract

The development of sustainable biorefining processes is essential for increasing the value of lignocellulosic resources and reducing the environmental footprint of the forest-based industry. Birch wood is one of Latvia's most abundant renewable feedstocks, yet current catalytic technologies for furfural production—primarily based on sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)—cause extensive cellulose degradation and generate sulfur-containing residues that hinder further valorization. This study proposes an integrated biorefining approach in which orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) is utilized as an alternative catalyst to selectively convert hemicellulose into furfural and acetic acid while preserving cellulose in birch veneer chips (BVC). The experimental plan was based on a full central composite circumscribed (CCC) response surface methodology (RSM) design, which consists of factorial points, axial (star) points, and centre points. In total, 26 experimental runs were performed, including 24 non-centre points (comprising both factorial and axial points ($\pm\alpha$)) and two centre points. The optimized conditions enabled high acetic acid yields (6.29–6.48% o.d.m., corresponding to 98–100% of theoretical), furfural yields of 8.75–10.41% o.d.m. (57–68% of theoretical), and exceptional glucan preservation (38.84–40.92% o.d.m., 94–99% of theoretical). Compared with sulfuric acid pretreatment, the H₃PO₄-based process significantly reduced cellulose degradation and improved the suitability of the resulting lignocellulosic residue for subsequent 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) production and other biorefining routes. The findings demonstrate that orthophosphoric acid catalysis is a promising pathway for integrating furfural extraction with cellulose-retentive pretreatment, thereby enhancing the sustainability, efficiency, and circularity of birch veneer chips' biomass utilization.

Keywords: lignocellulosic biomass; catalyzed hydrothermal pretreatment; furfural; acetic acid; birch veneer chips

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1. Introduction

The growing global demand for renewable materials and sustainable energy carriers has intensified interest in the valorization of lignocellulosic biomass into bio-based chemicals and materials [1]. Among the potential platform molecules derived from hemicellulose, furfural is particularly important as a precursor for fuels, solvents, resins, and polymers and is recognized as a key bio-based building block in several biorefinery roadmaps [2–4]. Its co-production with acetic acid, released from acetyl groups in hemicellulose during

hydrolysis, offers an economically attractive route to utilize the entire carbohydrate fraction of biomass in an integrated manner [5,6]. Efficient conversion of lignocellulosic feedstocks into furfural and acetic acid, while preserving cellulose for subsequent valorization, is therefore central to advancing circular bioeconomy concepts [7,8].

Conventional industrial furfural production is typically based on sulfuric-acid-catalyzed dehydration of pentoses under high-temperature conditions [9,10]. While effective, this approach suffers from serious drawbacks: extensive equipment corrosion, challenging acid recovery, formation of humins and degradation products, and environmentally problematic acidic effluents [11]. Several studies have highlighted these limitations and called for greener catalytic systems, including organic acids, solid acids, and alternative mineral acids with lower environmental impact [12–14]. In particular, the use of orthophosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) has attracted attention as a milder, less corrosive catalyst that can promote hemicellulose hydrolysis and furfural formation under hydrothermal conditions, while reducing cellulose degradation and simplifying downstream processing [15,16]. A comparison of other catalysts is not warranted, as sulfuric acid is currently the sole catalyst employed in the industrial furfural production process; however, Table 1 summarizes the differences in sulfuric acid and orthophosphoric acid [2].

Table 1. Comparison of catalysts—sulfuric acid and orthophosphoric acid.

Aspect	Sulfuric Acid (H_2SO_4)	Orthophosphoric Acid (H_3PO_4)
Acid strength	Strong acid (high proton availability)	Medium-strength, polyprotic acid
Catalytic efficiency	Very high; rapid hydrolysis of hemicellulose and cellulose	Moderate; slower hydrolysis, more selective
Reaction severity	Lower temperature and time needed	Requires higher temperature or longer residence time
Sugar degradation	High risk of degradation to furfural, 5-HMF, levulinic and formic acids	Lower degradation; better preservation of carbohydrates
Selectivity	Less selective; promotes side reactions	More selective toward targeted fractionation
Corrosiveness	Highly corrosive; requires corrosion-resistant reactors	Significantly less corrosive
Equipment and maintenance	Higher capital and maintenance costs	Lower equipment corrosion and maintenance costs
Environmental impact	Sulfate-rich wastewater; neutralization generates large salt loads	Phosphate-containing effluents; potential nutrient recovery
Catalyst recovery	Difficult; neutralization required	Easier recovery; non-volatile and reusable
Compatibility with downstream processing	Inhibits fermentation; requires detoxification	More compatible with enzymatic and catalytic steps
Safety considerations	High handling risk	Safer to handle
Industrial maturity	Widely used, well established	Increasing interest in biorefineries
Suitability for integrated biorefineries	Limited due to degradation and corrosion	High; supports cascade utilization

Sulfuric acid is preferred when high conversion rates are required but suffers from corrosion, sugar degradation, and environmental burden. Orthophosphoric acid offers better selectivity, lower corrosion, and easier integration into multi-product biorefineries, making it attractive for furfural and C6 cascade processes (bioethanol, lactic acid, in our case 5-HMF) [17,18].

Lignocellulosic feedstocks such as agricultural residues, hardwoods and softwoods have been widely explored for furfural production using hydrothermal or biphasic systems with various catalysts, demonstrating that process selectivity strongly depends on biomass composition, acid type, and reaction conditions [19,20]. Hydrothermal and steam-assisted

pretreatments have been identified as promising routes to combine fractionation and platform chemical generation in a single step, particularly when integrated into biorefinery schemes where solid residues are further upgraded to fuels, materials or high-value chemicals [21,22]. However, most reported systems either rely on sulfuric acid or are optimized primarily for furfural yield, with less emphasis on cellulose preservation and the quality of the lignocellulosic residue for subsequent processing [17,23,24]. Orthophosphoric acid selectively preserves cellulose during hydrothermal pretreatment compared to sulfuric acid due to differences in acid strength, reaction kinetics, and interactions with lignocellulosic polymers. As a moderately strong, polyprotic acid, orthophosphoric acid provides lower proton activity than sulfuric acid, resulting in milder hydrolytic conditions. This allows efficient cleavage of the more labile, amorphous hemicellulose while minimizing attack on the highly ordered and crystalline cellulose structure. Hemicellulose hydrolysis is further favored because of its acetylated and less crystalline nature, whereas cellulose requires harsher conditions for depolymerization [18].

In addition, orthophosphoric acid induces limited swelling of cellulose fibers by temporarily disrupting hydrogen bonding without extensive cleavage of β -1,4-glycosidic bonds, thereby maintaining cellulose polymer integrity. In contrast, sulfuric acid readily penetrates crystalline cellulose regions, causing rapid depolymerization and promoting secondary dehydration reactions of released sugars to 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, levulinic acid, and formic acid. Sulfuric acid also accelerates the formation of humins and pseudo-lignin, which can reduce cellulose quality and hinder downstream processing [25,26].

Overall, orthophosphoric acid enables a more controlled and selective fractionation of lignocellulosic biomass, preserving cellulose while efficiently removing hemicellulose. This selectivity makes it particularly suitable for integrated biorefinery concepts that rely on cascade processing and high-value utilization of all biomass fractions.

Birch wood is an abundant regional resource in Northern Europe and a major component of Latvia's forest-based bioeconomy [27]. Its relatively high hemicellulose content makes it an attractive feedstock for furfural and acetic acid production, while the cellulose-rich fraction can be further utilized for the generation of nanocellulose, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), bio-based composites, or functional materials in integrated biorefinery concepts [28,29]. Previous work has demonstrated the feasibility of catalyzed hydrothermal pretreatment and furfural production from different lignocellulosic residues, but systematic studies focusing on orthophosphoric-acid-catalyzed pretreatment of birch wood, with simultaneous optimization of furfural, acetic acid yield and cellulose retention, remain scarce [30,31].

In this work, we investigate the orthophosphoric-acid-catalyzed hydrothermal pretreatment of birch veneer chips with the aim to maximize furfural and acetic acid yields while preserving cellulose for further valorization (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme of the technological process.

The experimental plan was designed using a central composite circumscribed (CCC) response surface methodology (RSM). The design comprised factorial points, axial (star) points, and replicated center points, enabling systematic evaluation of the effects of pretreatment time, catalyst concentration, temperature, catalyst amount, steam flow rate, and initial moisture content on product formation and substrate integrity. The process performance is evaluated through chemical composition analysis, mass balance calculations, and product distribution. The results provide new insight into the interplay between catalytic conditions and product selectivity in a sulfur-free system and demonstrate the potential of birch wood veneer chips from plywood production as a feedstock for a green, integrated biorefinery based on orthophosphoric-acid-catalyzed hydrothermal processing.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials and Chemicals

Orthophosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) (85%), sulfuric acid (95–97%), D-(+)-cellobiose ($\geq 99\%$), D-(+)-glucose, ($\geq 99.5\%$), D-(+)-xylose ($\geq 99\%$), L-(+)-arabinose ($\geq 99\%$), D-(+)-galactose ($\geq 99\%$), D-(+)-mannose ($\geq 99\%$), furfural ($\geq 98.5\%$), acetic acid ($\geq 99.5\%$), 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) ($\geq 98.5\%$), levulinic acid ($\geq 98\%$), and formic acid ($\geq 99\%$) were purchased from Merck (Eschenstr. 582,024 Taufkirchen, Germany) and used without further purification.

2.2. Characterization of Feedstock

Birch (*Betula pendula*) veneer chips were supplied by the Latvijas Finieris (Bolderaja, Latvia), a company that manufactures plywood, and used as is without any further mechanical modification. Birch veneer chips are generated as a by-product of plywood manufacturing. The material originates from the veneer log peeling process, representing the outer layers of birch wood, and is characterized by a uniform particle size and low level of contamination, making it suitable for lignocellulosic biorefining applications. The samples were air-dried to a moisture content of 45 ± 2 wt.%. Initially, we quantified the extractives in the BVC, adhering to the TAPPI 204 cm-07 standard [32]. The extraction was carried out using Knöfler-Böhm extractors with acetone, and it lasted for 6 h. To isolate the structural carbohydrates (like glucose, xylose, galactose, arabinose, and mannose) from the BVC samples, we employed a two-stage sulfuric acid hydrolysis method according to the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) standard TP-510-42618 [33]. Saccharide concentrations were then determined using HPLC on a Shimadzu LC20AD liquid chromatograph equipped with a Shimadzu RID 10A RI detector and a Thermo Scientific HyperREZ XP Carbohydrates Pb^{2+} column (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). The analysis used Milli-Q water as a mobile phase with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min at an oven temperature of 70 °C. Before the HPLC assessments, barium carbonate was employed to counteract sulfuric acid effects. Moreover, we evaluated by-products of the hydrolysis process, including formic acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, and furfural, using HPLC but without prior neutralization. This particular analysis utilized a Shodex Sugar SH-1821 column (Shodex/Resonac Corporation (formerly Showa Denko K.K.), Kawasaki, Japan) at 50 °C, with 0.005 M H_2SO_4 as the eluent, and maintained a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. All analytical standards were sourced from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Finally, acid-insoluble lignin and ash content were assessed based on the NREL TP-510-42618 [33] and TP-510-42622 [34] standards, respectively.

2.3. Hydrothermal Pretreatment Procedure

Birch veneer chips (BVC) were mixed with a catalyst solution in a specially designed blade-type mixer. A diluted orthophosphoric acid solution of varying concentration was used as the catalyst. In each experiment, approximately 1140 g (o.d.m.) of BVC (excluding

the catalyst) were used, while the catalyst amount was adjusted according to the experimental design. Following the mixing step, the catalyst-impregnated material was subjected to continuous superheated steam treatment in a custom-built bench-scale reactor system (Figure 2), designed to simulate the industrial furfural production process at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6. The main reactor chamber had a diameter of 110 mm, a height of 1450 mm, a total volume of 13.7 L, and a maximum operating pressure of 1.2 MPa. The reactor was equipped with a dual heat-insulation system and automated temperature-control equipment to maintain a stable reaction zone temperature throughout the process under varying operational conditions. Operating at TRL 6 underscores the reactor's importance, as it enables process validation in a relevant industrial environment, providing reliable data for scale-up and demonstrating the practical feasibility of the proposed biorefining approach.

Figure 2. Scheme of the reactor system.

After the treatment process, the obtained hydrolysate contained several value-added products, including formic acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, 5-HMF, and furfural. The concentrations of these compounds were analyzed using HPLC (Shimadzu LC20AD liquid chromatograph, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with an RI detector (Shimadzu RID-10A, Kyoto, Japan) and a Shodex Sugar SH-1821 column (Shodex/Resonac Corporation (formerly Showa Denko K.K.), Kawasaki, Japan), following the method described in Section 2.2.

The treated birch veneer chips (lignocellulosic residue, LCR) were discharged from the reactor and weighed, and their moisture content was determined using an automatic infrared moisture analyzer (Shimadzu MOC-120H, Kyoto, Japan), following the NREL/TP-510-42621 [35] standard. Prior to chemical analysis, the BVC LCR was dried to a moisture content of 10% in a Venticell 707 ECO (MMM Group, Planegg, Germany), forced-air circulation chamber at 55 °C for 24 h and then milled in a Retsch GmbH SM100 (Haan, Germany) cutting mill using a 0.75 mm sieve.

The carbohydrate content, acetyl groups, and acid-soluble and acid-insoluble lignin in the LCR were quantified according to the NREL TP-510-42618 [34] standard. Details of the HPLC procedures are provided in Section 2.2. All product yields were calculated on an oven-dried basis relative to the initial feedstock. For each condition, two parallel experiments were performed, and the results are presented as average values, with all relative standard deviations (RSD) being below 5%.

2.4. Experimental Design

Previous studies [30,31] showed that there are a lot of technological parameters that can affect the outcome of target biobased products. Therefore, the effect of the variables of temperature (T), catalyst amount (m), treatment time (τ) and steam flow rate (v) has been studied (see Table 2).

Table 2. The parameter levels used in the experimental design.

Parameter	Symbol	Actual Factor Level				
		$-\alpha$	Low	Centre	High	$+\alpha$
Temperature (T)	°C	150	155	165	175	180
Catalyst amount (m)	% o.d.m.	1.75	2.5	4	5.5	6.25
Treatment time (τ)	min	20	30	50	70	80
Steam flow rate (v)	mL/min	70	80	100	120	130

In turn, the constant factors were the moisture of the raw material (w)—45%—and catalyst (H_3PO_4) concentration (c)—55%. The experimental plan was based on a full central composite circumscribed (CCC) response surface methodology (RSM) design, which consists of factorial points, axial (star) points, and centre points. In total, 26 experimental runs were performed, including 24 non-centre points (comprising both factorial and axial points ($\pm\alpha$) and two centre points (Runs 13 and 17 identified as the central points. Data analysis was performed using Design-Expert 13 software (Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, MN, USA). After their implementation, it was possible to judge the direction in which to continue the experimental work. Experimental work was performed on an original bench-scale reactor system (described in Section 2.3). A total of 26 experimental trials were performed with 2 parallel runs.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Analysis of the Raw Material

The chemical composition of the raw material plays a key role in determining the efficiency and economic viability of biorefining processes. Birch veneer chips (BVC), a widely available byproduct of the Latvian wood-processing industry, represent a promising lignocellulosic feedstock due to their relatively high cellulose content and well-defined structural composition. To assess the potential of BVC for the integrated production of furfural, acetic acid, and cellulose-rich lignocellulosic residue (LCR), a detailed analysis of their chemical constituents was performed according to NREL standard methods. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Chemical composition of birch veneer chips.

Compound	Amount (% of o.d.m.)
Extractives (acetone)	4.24 ± 0.06
Glucan	41.51 ± 0.04
Xylan	20.81 ± 0.04
Galactan	1.00 ± 0.05
Arabinan	0.66 ± 0.06
Mannan	0.90 ± 0.01
Acid-insoluble residue (Klason lignin)	19.6 ± 0.04
Acid-soluble lignin	3.71 ± 0.06
Ash	0.60 ± 0.01
Acetyl groups	4.60 ± 0.05

Similar to other hardwood materials, BVC consist predominantly of cellulose (glucan), hemicellulose (mainly xylan), and lignin. In the analyzed samples, glucan was the major component (41.51% of o.d.m. ± 0.04%), followed by xylan (20.81% of o.d.m. ± 0.04%), while lignin accounted for 19.6% of o.d.m. ± 0.04%. Birch wood also contained 4.60% of o.d.m. ± 0.05% acetyl groups, which play a crucial role in the formation of acetic acid and hemicellulose hydrolysis during hydrothermal or acid-catalyzed pretreatment. Compared

to agricultural residues such as oat husks, the lower ash content and higher carbohydrate fraction of BVC make them particularly attractive for high-purity chemical production and downstream material applications.

Given this composition, birch veneer chips offer strong potential for the production of C5-derived platform chemicals. The high xylan content makes BVC suitable for efficient furfural production, while the presence of acetyl groups ensures simultaneous formation of acetic acid as a value-added coproduct. At the same time, the high proportion of cellulose provides a favorable foundation for integrated biorefining strategies aimed at preserving cellulose for subsequent valorization—such as enzymatic hydrolysis, nanocellulose production, or bio-based material applications.

3.2. Furfural Production

The efficiency of furfural and acetic acid production from lignocellulosic biomass is strongly dependent on pretreatment conditions such as temperature, catalyst concentration, treatment duration, and steam flow rate. In the present study, 26 experiments were conducted to systematically evaluate the influence of these parameters on the yields of furfural and acetic acid produced from birch veneer chips (BVCs) using orthophosphoric acid as a catalyst. The obtained experimental results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Furfural and acetic acid yield in the hydrolysis condensates according to the CCC experimental design.

Run	Temperature, (T)	Catalyst Amount, (m)	Treatment Time, (τ)	Steam Flow Rate (v)	Furfural	Acetic Acid
	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	wt. %	min	mL/min	% of o.d.m.	% of o.d.m.
1	155	2.50	30	120	0.64 \pm 0.06	2.47 \pm 0.01
2	155	2.50	70	120	2.13 \pm 0.02	4.80 \pm 0.01
3	155	5.50	70	80	3.60 \pm 0.05	5.26 \pm 0.02
4	165	1.75	50	100	3.08 \pm 0.08	4.83 \pm 0.03
5	175	5.50	70	120	10.11 \pm 0.08	5.71 \pm 0.04
6	155	5.50	30	80	1.41 \pm 0.05	3.38 \pm 0.03
7	155	5.50	30	120	1.67 \pm 0.01	4.10 \pm 0.01
8	175	2.50	70	120	9.63 \pm 0.06	6.23 \pm 0.02
9	150	4.00	50	100	1.32 \pm 0.08	4.06 \pm 0.04
10	165	4.00	80	100	7.41 \pm 0.02	5.83 \pm 0.02
11	155	5.50	70	120	4.32 \pm 0.01	5.55 \pm 0.03
12	165	4.00	20	100	2.79 \pm 0.03	2.77 \pm 0.01
13	165	4.00	50	100	4.23 \pm 0.07	5.09 \pm 0.01
14	175	2.50	70	80	5.30 \pm 0.02	5.69 \pm 0.03
15	165	4.00	50	130	4.96 \pm 0.01	5.47 \pm 0.01
16	175	2.50	30	80	3.22 \pm 0.06	3.34 \pm 0.02
17	165	4.00	50	100	4.67 \pm 0.01	5.11 \pm 0.02
18	155	2.50	30	80	0.57 \pm 0.01	1.83 \pm 0.01
19	175	5.50	30	80	5.38 \pm 0.03	4.33 \pm 0.03
20	155	2.50	70	80	2.39 \pm 0.05	4.69 \pm 0.02
21	180	4.00	50	100	9.35 \pm 0.01	5.61 \pm 0.01
22	165	6.25	50	100	6.07 \pm 0.06	5.53 \pm 0.03
23	175	5.50	30	120	5.90 \pm 0.06	4.79 \pm 0.02
24	175	5.50	70	80	9.87 \pm 0.03	5.92 \pm 0.02
25	175	2.50	30	120	4.57 \pm 0.04	4.92 \pm 0.03
26	165	4.00	50	70	4.63 \pm 0.05	5.03 \pm 0.02

Furfural yields ranged from 0.57% to 10.11% (of o.d.m.), demonstrating a significant variation depending on process conditions. As expected, higher temperatures substantially

enhanced furfural formation. Experiments performed at 175–180 °C consistently generated the highest yields, with the maximum value (10.11%) obtained at 175 °C, 5.50 wt.% catalyst, 70 min, and a steam flow rate of 120 mL/min (Run 5).

Lower temperature experiments (150–155 °C) produced markedly reduced furfural yields (typically $\leq 3\%$), highlighting the importance of thermal acceleration in pentose dehydration reactions. Treatment duration also played a crucial role: increasing the reaction time from 30 min to 70 min significantly enhanced furfural yields at moderate temperatures (e.g., Run 1 vs. Run 2; Run 18 vs. Run 20).

Catalyst amount exhibited a synergistic effect with temperature. While moderate catalyst loadings (2.50–4.00 wt.%) facilitated substantial conversion, the highest yields were generally observed when the catalyst amount reached 5.50–6.25 wt.% (e.g., Runs 5, 10, 11, 22, 24). This suggests that orthophosphoric acid effectively accelerates hemicellulose hydrolysis under intensified process conditions but remains milder toward cellulose, supporting the overall process objective.

Acetic acid yields were less sensitive to temperature than furfural yields, varying from 1.83% to 6.23% (of o.d.m.). This trend is consistent with the known mechanism of acetyl group cleavage from xylan chains, which proceeds efficiently at moderate temperatures. The highest yield (6.23%) was obtained at 175 °C, 2.50 wt.% catalyst, 70 min and a steam flow rate of 120 mL/min (Run 8), indicating that a high catalyst concentration is not required for effective acetyl hydrolysis.

Across most experiments, acetic acid yields remained in the range of 4.5–6.0%, suggesting a relatively stable release of acetyl groups regardless of small differences in operational conditions. This consistency is advantageous for biorefinery integration, as acetic acid represents a valuable coproduct contributing to the economic feasibility of the process.

Furfural formation strongly depends on temperature, catalyst loading, and treatment time, showing clear maxima under more severe operating conditions. Acetic acid formation is more robust, with relatively high yields obtained across a wide parameter range. This behavior reflects the chemical pathways involved: furfural synthesis requires pentose dehydration and is therefore highly dependent on acidic catalytic intensity, while acetic acid formation is largely governed by acetyl group cleavage, which proceeds efficiently even under moderate conditions.

In addition to furfural and acetic acid, several secondary degradation products—namely formic acid, levulinic acid, and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF)—were detected in the hydrolysates obtained from birch veneer chip (BVC) pretreatment. Their formation is predominantly associated with side reactions of pentose and hexose sugars under acidic and thermally intensified conditions. The yields of these compounds for all 26 experiments are presented in Figure 3.

Formic acid was the most abundant of the three compounds, with yields ranging from 0.20% to 0.74% (o.d.m.). The highest concentrations were observed in experiments performed at elevated temperatures (≥ 175 °C) and higher catalyst loadings. For instance, Runs 5, 7, 8, 14, and 24 demonstrated the highest formic acid production, each exceeding 0.55% of o.d.m. This trend aligns with known degradation pathways, in which pentoses and furfural undergo subsequent decomposition to formic acid under severe reaction conditions.

Levulinic acid was produced in comparatively small quantities, typically within the range of 0.01–0.05% (o.d.m.). This compound is formed through the rehydration of 5-HMF originating from hexose degradation, indicating some degree of cellulose or glucose conversion despite the generally mild effect of orthophosphoric acid on cellulose. The slightly elevated levulinic acid yields in Runs 5, 8, 14, and 24 correspond with the highest temperature and longest residence time experiments, suggesting that harsher conditions promote limited hexose decomposition. Overall, the consistently low levulinic

acid levels confirm that cellulose degradation remained minimal, supporting the suitability of orthophosphoric acid for cellulose-preserving pretreatment.

Figure 3. The admixture yield (% of o.d.m.) in the hydrolysis condensates.

5-HMF yields were also relatively low, ranging from 0.01% to 0.05% (o.d.m.), with the highest production reported for Runs 3, 5, 7, 8, and 24. Since 5-HMF formation requires hexose dehydration, its presence indicates only a minor conversion of glucose-rich fractions under the studied conditions. This further confirms that the pretreatment selectively targets hemicellulose, leaving the cellulose fraction largely intact for subsequent biorefining steps. Notably, trends in 5-HMF formation closely mirrored those of levulinic acid, consistent with their shared reaction pathways.

To evaluate the influence of selected treatment parameters on furfural yield, the design matrix of experimental conditions with the corresponding furfural yields (Table 2) was subjected to regression analysis, generating the following quadratic equation in actual values (Equation (1)):

$$\text{Furfural} = 93.72 - 0.62(T) - 20.84(m) - 0.32(\tau) - 1.08(v) + 0.14(T \cdot m) + 0.002(T \cdot \tau) + 0.007(T \cdot v) + 0.20(m \cdot v) - 0.12(m^2) - 0.0013(T \cdot m \cdot v) \quad (1)$$

According to the ANOVA test (Table 5), the model presented a high value for the regression coefficient ($R^2 = 0.97$). The value of the adjusted determination coefficient (adjusted $R^2 = 0.96$) was also high, indicating a high significance of the model.

As indicated in Figure 4, the furfural yield increased with increasing treatment temperature and time across all studied conditions. As expected, the lowest amounts of furfural were obtained at the lowest values of both variables, where the hydrolysis and dehydration reactions proceeded only to a limited extent. At the lowest catalyst amount and steam flow rate (Figure 4A), the response surface is relatively flat, showing that increases in temperature and time resulted in only a moderate rise in furfural production. Under these mild conditions, the sensitivity of furfural formation to temperature and time is noticeably lower than at higher catalyst loadings.

Table 5. The ANOVA for reduced cubic model (furfural).

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-Value	
Model	194.70	10	19.47	54.03	<0.0001	significant
A-Temp.	118.54	1	118.54	328.97	<0.0001	
B-Cat. am.	16.33	1	16.33	45.31	<0.0001	
C-Time	46.64	1	46.64	129.43	<0.0001	
D-SFR	2.91	1	2.91	8.08	0.0124	
AB	0.6683	1	0.6683	1.85	0.1933	
AC	3.70	1	3.70	10.26	0.0059	
AD	2.00	1	2.00	5.54	0.0327	
BD	0.8789	1	0.8789	2.44	0.1392	
B ²	0.7334	1	0.7334	2.04	0.1742	
ABD	2.32	1	2.32	6.43	0.0228	
Residual	5.40	15	0.3603			
Lack of Fit	5.31	14	0.3791	3.92	0.3788	not significant
Pure Error	0.0968	1	0.0968			
Cor Total	200.11	25				

Figure 4. The effect of treatment time and temperature on the furfural yield (% o.d.m.) at the lowest (A), medium (B), and highest (C) studied catalyst amount (wt.%) and steam flow rate (mL/min) according to the obtained mathematical model. The lowest catalyst amount—2.5 wt.%, medium—4 wt.%, and highest—5.5 wt.%. The lowest steam flow rate—80 mL/min, medium—100 mL/min, and highest—120 mL/min.

At medium catalyst amounts and steam flow (Figure 4B), the interaction between treatment time and temperature becomes more pronounced, and the response surface assumes an almost linear slope. In this region, the model suggests that the optimal temperature and time should be searched within the intervals of approximately 158–170 °C and 35–60 min, where furfural formation increases steadily without indications of strong curvature. These trends indicate that at medium severity, the combined effect of temperature and time is synergistic and predictable within the studied range.

When the catalyst amount and steam flow are at their highest values (Figure 4C), the optimal parameter range broadens further, extending from 155 to 170 °C and 30 to 70 min. However, the model indicates that although the region of potentially suitable severity widens, the maximum furfural yield obtained at these high-severity conditions is not necessarily higher than that observed at medium catalyst loading. This suggests that increasing severity beyond a certain point does not proportionally increase the furfural yield, most likely due to the onset of secondary reactions and furfural degradation.

Therefore, based on the model predictions, the optimal conditions for maximizing furfural yield from birch veneer chips should be sought at intermediate catalyst amounts and steam flow levels, combined with treatment temperatures of approximately 160–170 °C and processing times of 35–60 min. These conditions offer the best balance between effective hemicellulose conversion and avoidance of furfural loss due to condensation or degradation reactions.

Temperature and treatment time emerged as the most influential factors governing furfural yield, both individually and in interaction. This behavior is consistent with the kinetics of hemicellulose depolymerization and pentose dehydration reactions. Increasing temperature accelerates (i) xylan hydrolysis to xylose and oligomers and (ii) the subsequent acid-catalyzed dehydration of pentoses to furfural. Longer residence times allow these reactions to proceed closer to completion, particularly under moderate catalytic intensity. However, the response surfaces indicate diminishing returns at the highest severities, especially at elevated temperatures combined with long treatment times. This curvature reflects the onset of secondary reactions, including furfural condensation, resinification, and degradation to formic acid and other low-molecular-weight compounds. Thus, while temperature–time synergy is essential for furfural formation, excessive severity shifts the reaction network toward degradation pathways rather than productive dehydration.

The catalyst amount significantly influences the availability of protons for hydrolytic and dehydration reactions. At low catalyst loadings, hemicellulose hydrolysis is incomplete, limiting the supply of free pentoses and leading to low furfural yields even at elevated temperatures. As catalyst loading increases, the combined effects of enhanced xylan depolymerization and accelerated pentose dehydration become evident, explaining the strong main effect of catalyst amount and its interaction with temperature and time.

Notably, the interaction terms involving catalyst amount (e.g., temperature \times catalyst and time \times catalyst) highlight that catalyst effectiveness is conditional rather than independent. Orthophosphoric acid is a relatively mild acid; therefore, its catalytic strength becomes significant only when thermal energy and sufficient reaction time are provided. This explains why higher catalyst concentrations alone do not guarantee maximum furfural yields unless coupled with adequate temperature and residence time.

At the same time, the models indicate that excessive catalyst loading contributes to increased cellulose degradation at high severity. This is mechanistically expected, as prolonged exposure to acidic conditions at elevated temperatures promotes cleavage of β -1,4-glycosidic bonds in cellulose, albeit at a slower rate than hemicellulose degradation. The observed curvature in the cellulose response surfaces reflects this transition from selective hemicellulose removal to partial cellulose hydrolysis.

The interaction between steam flow rate and temperature on the furfural yield at the lowest, medium, and highest studied catalyst amounts and treatment times is illustrated in Figure 5. At the lowest catalyst amount (2.5 wt.%) and shortest treatment time (30 min) (Figure 5A), the modelled surface is nearly flat, indicating that variations in steam flow rate and temperature have only a minor effect on furfural formation under these mild conditions. Only a slight increase in furfural yield is observed toward the higher end of both variables, suggesting limited pentose conversion.

By increasing the catalyst amount to 4 wt.% and the treatment time to 50 min (Figure 5B), the interaction between steam flow rate and temperature becomes more noticeable, and the response surface develops a clearer upward slope. In this region, higher temperatures lead to a stronger increase in furfural yield than changes in steam flow rate, although the latter still contributes to gradual enhancement of the dehydration process. The model predicts that furfural yield can increase from approximately 6% to 9% o.d.m. as both variables approach their upper limits.

At the highest catalyst amount (5.5 wt.%) and the longest treatment time (70 min) (Figure 5C), the obtained surface shows a pronounced curvature, indicating a strong interaction between steam flow rate and temperature. According to the model, the highest furfural yields are obtained at the combination of the highest temperature and the highest steam flow rate studied. The steep slope of the surface in this region suggests that steam flow becomes more influential at high severity, likely due to improved removal of

volatile furfural and reduced degradation. This behavior demonstrates that under intensified conditions, both temperature and steam flow rate act synergistically to maximize furfural recovery.

Figure 5. The effect of steam flow rate and temperature on the furfural yield (% o.d.m.) at the lowest (A), medium (B), and highest (C) studied catalyst amount (wt.%) and time (min) according to the obtained mathematical model. The lowest catalyst amount—2.5 wt.%, medium—4 wt.%, and highest—5.5 wt.%. The lowest time—30 min, medium—50 min, and highest—70 min.

Steam flow rate exhibits a weaker main effect compared to temperature and time, but its interaction terms become significant at higher severities. This behavior can be explained by the dual role of steam in the system. First, steam acts as a heat and mass transfer medium, facilitating uniform temperature distribution and promoting the removal of volatile products such as furfural from the reaction zone. At low severity, furfural formation is limited by reaction kinetics rather than mass transfer; therefore, increasing steam flow has little impact. This explains the relatively flat response surfaces observed under mild conditions.

At higher temperatures, catalyst loadings, and longer treatment times, steam flow becomes increasingly important. Rapid removal of furfural reduces its residence time in the acidic environment, thereby limiting secondary degradation and condensation reactions. This mechanistic effect accounts for the strong interaction between the steam flow rate and temperature observed at high severity and explains why maximum furfural yields are often achieved at the upper end of the steam flow range.

3.3. Chemical Composition of Lignocellulosic Residue

The chemical composition of the lignocellulosic residues (LCRs) obtained after hydrothermal pretreatment of birch veneer chips varied considerably depending on the process temperature, catalyst loading, steam flow rate, and treatment time (Table 6).

In all experiments, cellulose (glucan) remained the dominant structural component of the LCR. Glucan contents typically ranged between approximately 43% and 55% of the dry LCR mass, with the highest values observed at more severe pretreatment conditions, such as elevated temperatures (≥ 170 °C), higher catalyst amount, and longer treatment times. The preservation of such a high proportion of glucan demonstrates that orthophosphoric acid, even under intensified reaction conditions, does not promote substantial cellulose degradation. This is a critical advantage for integrated biorefining, as a cellulose-rich residue enables subsequent conversion pathways and increases the overall economic value of the process.

Table 6. The chemical composition of obtained birch veneer chip LC after furfural production.

Run	BVC LC	Acid-Insoluble Residue	Glucan	Xylan	Arabinan	Galactan	Mannan	Acetyl Groups
	% o.d.m.	% LC						
1	93.11	22.70 ± 0.02	43.89 ± 0.09	20.66 ± 0.07	0.48 ± 0.01	1.14 ± 0.07	1.12 ± 0.03	1.76 ± 0.02
2	88.97	25.06 ± 0.09	45.04 ± 0.23	19.37 ± 0.13	0.42 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.03
3	81.26	25.89 ± 0.22	47.81 ± 0.09	16.03 ± 0.10	0.45 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.00
4	82.30	26.29 ± 0.14	49.12 ± 0.22	16.03 ± 0.11	0.43 ± 0.00	1.46 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.05	0.72 ± 0.00
5	68.18	36.24 ± 0.11	51.54 ± 0.20	2.72 ± 0.00	0.28 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.01
6	89.72	23.85 ± 0.06	43.48 ± 0.11	19.05 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.01	1.45 ± 0.01	1.11 ± 0.00	0.88 ± 0.00
7	86.47	24.02 ± 0.06	43.27 ± 0.19	18.04 ± 0.07	0.35 ± 0.00	0.98 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.03
8	74.24	32.76 ± 0.08	53.23 ± 0.24	6.14 ± 0.07	0.33 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.05	0.48 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.03
9	85.08	23.47 ± 0.10	44.03 ± 0.06	20.44 ± 0.13	0.54 ± 0.04	1.68 ± 0.07	1.06 ± 0.08	1.04 ± 0.01
10	70.66	31.04 ± 0.01	52.29 ± 0.23	9.06 ± 0.11	0.34 ± 0.00	1.15 ± 0.00	0.38 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.01
11	78.83	26.62 ± 0.01	47.97 ± 0.25	14.45 ± 0.20	0.39 ± 0.02	1.31 ± 0.08	0.76 ± 0.03	0.32 ± 0.01
12	84.10	24.42 ± 0.07	44.15 ± 0.18	18.55 ± 0.18	0.58 ± 0.07	1.77 ± 0.11	0.93 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.01
13	82.03	28.01 ± 0.21	48.59 ± 0.20	14.35 ± 0.13	0.42 ± 0.00	1.46 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.01
14	71.01	33.96 ± 0.35	55.07 ± 0.20	6.17 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.01
15	79.82	27.74 ± 0.16	48.83 ± 0.09	13.36 ± 0.11	0.42 ± 0.01	1.28 ± 0.05	1.35 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.00
16	83.20	28.78 ± 0.28	49.89 ± 0.50	13.98 ± 0.09	0.40 ± 0.01	1.41 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.18	0.48 ± 0.01
17	79.95	28.21 ± 0.07	48.73 ± 0.24	13.49 ± 0.07	0.38 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.05	0.77 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.00
18	94.48	22.77 ± 0.05	44.42 ± 0.09	21.16 ± 0.03	0.56 ± 0.02	1.95 ± 0.10	1.12 ± 0.03	1.76 ± 0.04
19	77.57	30.47 ± 0.17	50.88 ± 0.27	9.84 ± 0.11	0.39 ± 0.07	1.42 ± 0.26	0.62 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.01
20	90.70	24.75 ± 0.04	45.22 ± 0.19	19.08 ± 0.13	0.44 ± 0.01	1.64 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.00
21	70.04	36.17 ± 0.01	51.19 ± 0.32	3.64 ± 0.00	0.23 ± 0.01	0.85 ± 0.02	0.12 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01
22	74.79	28.83 ± 0.12	49.10 ± 0.34	10.63 ± 0.06	0.40 ± 0.01	1.23 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.13	0.24 ± 0.01
23	75.27	31.09 ± 0.18	49.50 ± 0.45	9.52 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.00	1.41 ± 0.10	0.56 ± 0.00	0.27 ± 0.01
24	71.03	35.84 ± 0.23	52.11 ± 0.45	3.12 ± 0.07	0.29 ± 0.01	0.82 ± 0.11	0.11 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.01
25	88.17	29.11 ± 0.36	48.91 ± 0.27	14.08 ± 0.17	0.41 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.11	0.89 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.01
26	79.07	28.21 ± 0.02	49.08 ± 0.18	12.39 ± 0.08	0.38 ± 0.01	1.30 ± 0.07	0.66 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.01

In contrast to cellulose, hemicellulosic components were highly susceptible to hydrothermal and acid-catalyzed degradation. Xylan, the major hemicellulosic sugar in birch wood, showed a pronounced decline under harsher pretreatment conditions. Its content decreased from ~20–21% under milder conditions to below 3–6% in the most severe experiments. Similar trends were observed for other non-cellulosic sugars: arabinan declined to 0.28–0.33%, galactan decreased to ~0.8–1.0%, and mannan content dropped to as low as 0.11–0.35%. These reductions clearly indicate extensive hemicellulose solubilization and conversion, which aligns with the observed formation of furfural and acetic acid in the hydrolysates.

Acetyl groups also diminished sharply as reaction severity increased. Their levels ranged from ~1.7–1.8% in mildly treated residues to only ~0.1–0.3% in more intensively treated samples. Since hydrolysis of acetyl groups generates acetic acid, this decrease is consistent with the acetic acid yields described for the liquid phase.

As a consequence of hemicellulose removal, the acid-insoluble residue (AIR), which corresponds primarily to lignin, became more concentrated in the LCR. AIR values increased from approximately 22–26% in mild treatments to ~32–36% under the most severe conditions. This lignin enrichment is typical for hydrothermal pretreatment because lignin is less susceptible to depolymerization under these conditions. The resulting lignin-rich residues may have potential value in applications such as bio-based binders or soil amendments.

Overall, the compositional changes observed across the experimental range demonstrate that the pretreatment conditions used in this study effectively separate hemicellulose into the liquid phase while preserving cellulose in the solid residue. This behavior is essential for integrated biorefining, as it supports both the production of furfural and acetic acid from hemicellulose-derived intermediates and the retention of a cellulose-rich lignocellulosic residue suitable for further valorization. The strong correlation between pretreatment

severity and the distribution of carbohydrates, lignin, and acetyl groups provides a clear understanding of how orthophosphoric-acid-catalyzed steam pretreatment modulates the chemical composition of birch veneer chips and enables process optimization.

To better evaluate the effect of treatment process parameters on the losses of glucan (in the following figures expressed as cellulose), the design matrix of experimental conditions with the corresponding glucan yield in the lignocellulosic residue (Table 6) was subjected to regression analysis using Design Expert software (version 11), generating the following quadratic equation in actual values (Equation (2)):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cellulose} = & +719.80 - 8.40(T) - 22.20(m) - 15.89(\tau) - 0.04(v) + 0.11(T \cdot m) + 0.20(\tau \cdot T) - 0.0006(v \cdot T) \\ & + 0.43(m \cdot \tau) + 0.040(m \cdot v) + 0.002(\tau \cdot v) + 0.03(T^2) + 0.61(m^2) - 0.03(\tau^2) + 0.0002(v^2) - 0.003(T \cdot m \cdot \tau) \\ & - 0.00002(T \cdot \tau \cdot v) + 0.0001(m \cdot \tau \cdot v) - 0.0006(T^2 \cdot \tau) + 0.0002(T \cdot \tau^2) - 0.005(m^2 \cdot v) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

According to the ANOVA test (Table 7) the regression coefficient is 0.9997, but the value of the adjusted determination coefficient is 0.998.

Table 7. The ANOVA for reduced cubic model (cellulose).

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-Value	
Model	281.17	20	14.06	952.67	<0.0001	significant
A-Temp.	27.53	1	27.53	1865.44	<0.0001	
B-Cat. am.	0.0756	1	0.0756	5.12	0.0730	
C-Time	33.46	1	33.46	2267.15	<0.0001	
D-SFR	0.0578	1	0.0578	3.92	0.1047	
AB	2.98	1	2.98	201.64	<0.0001	
AC	0.0756	1	0.0756	5.12	0.0730	
AD	1.28	1	1.28	86.53	0.0002	
BC	0.0506	1	0.0506	3.43	0.1232	
BD	0.2209	1	0.2209	14.97	0.0118	
CD	0.0256	1	0.0256	1.73	0.2449	
A ²	2.33	1	2.33	157.62	<0.0001	
B ²	0.4862	1	0.4862	32.95	0.0022	
C ²	0.4301	1	0.4301	29.14	0.0029	
D ²	0.0805	1	0.0805	5.45	0.0668	
ABC	10.37	1	10.37	702.61	<0.0001	
ACD	0.0702	1	0.0702	4.76	0.0810	
BCD	0.0650	1	0.0650	4.41	0.0899	
A ² C	5.50	1	5.50	372.87	<0.0001	
AC ²	1.91	1	1.91	129.16	<0.0001	
B ² D	0.1865	1	0.1865	12.64	0.0163	
Residual	0.0738	5	0.0148			
Lack of Fit	0.0576	4	0.0144	0.8887	0.6514	not significant
Pure Error	0.0162	1	0.0162			
Cor Total	281.24	25				

As shown in Figure 6, cellulose loss increases progressively with rising treatment severity. The main factors influencing cellulose degradation are temperature, catalyst amount, and treatment time, while steam flow rate has a secondary but noticeable effect by influencing the removal of volatile products from the reaction zone. Across all surfaces, cellulose degradation occurs almost monotonically with increasing temperature, reflecting the typical behavior of lignocellulosic systems under acid-assisted thermal pretreatment.

At the lowest catalyst amount (2.5 wt.%) and shortest treatment time (30 min) (Figure 6A), cellulose preservation is the highest, and the response surface displays only a gentle downward slope. Under these mild conditions, cellulose content remains close to its initial level (above ~52% o.d. LC), confirming that the structural polysaccharide fraction of birch veneer chips is well protected from hydrolytic cleavage. This is desirable when

the aim of biorefining is to maximize furfural production from hemicellulose-derived C5 carbohydrates while retaining cellulose for further valorization pathways.

Figure 6. Effect of steam flow rate and temperature on the cellulose loss at the lowest (A), medium (B), and highest (C) studied catalyst amount and treatment time according to the obtained mathematical model. The lowest catalyst amount—2.5 wt.%, medium—4 wt.%, and highest—5.5 wt.%. The lowest treatment time—30 min, medium—50 min, and highest—70 min.

At medium catalyst amount (4 wt.%) and treatment time (50 min) (Figure 6B), the effect of temperature on cellulose degradation becomes more pronounced. The decrease in cellulose content is gradual but more substantial than under mild conditions, yielding values in the range of approximately 48–51% o.d. LC. Within this region, the influence of steam flow rate is limited, indicating that temperature is the dominant factor governing cellulose stability. These results show that although moderate severity enhances furfural production (Section 3.2), it simultaneously accelerates cellulose degradation.

At the highest catalyst amount (5.5 wt.%) and longest treatment time (70 min) (Figure 6C), the model predicts a clear curvature of the response surface, indicating a strong interaction between temperature and steam flow rate. Under these severe conditions, cellulose losses become significantly larger, with values decreasing to ~46% o.d. LC. Higher steam flow rates help mitigate degradation slightly, likely by removing acidic and volatile by-products that would otherwise catalyze further cellulose hydrolysis. Nevertheless, the overall trend demonstrates that high catalyst loading combined with prolonged exposure to elevated temperatures substantially increases cellulose degradation.

For cellulose preservation, increased steam flow slightly mitigates degradation under severe conditions by diluting acidic intermediates and facilitating their removal. However, this protective effect is secondary compared to the dominant influence of temperature and time, which govern the intrinsic stability of cellulose.

Overall, these results show that achieving high furfural yields requires increasing the severity of the treatment—higher temperatures, greater catalyst amounts, and longer reaction times—which inevitably leads to greater cellulose loss. Therefore, a balance must be found between maximizing furfural formation and preserving cellulose as a high-value product in an integrated birch biorefining approach.

4. Conclusions

1. This study demonstrates that orthophosphoric-acid-catalyzed hydrothermal pretreatment provides an effective and sustainable strategy for the integrated production of furfural, acetic acid, and a cellulose-rich lignocellulosic residue (LCR) from birch veneer chips. The CCC/RSM design enabled a detailed evaluation of critical process parameters—the temperature, catalyst amount, treatment time, and steam flow rate revealed clear trends governing the conversion and preservation of the major biomass constituents.

2. Furfural formation was strongly dependent on treatment severity, with the temperature, catalyst amount, and treatment time acting as the dominant factors. Under optimized conditions, furfural yields of 8.75–10.41% o.d.m. (57–68% of the theoretical maximum) were achieved. Acetic acid yields were consistently high across most experimental conditions (6.29–6.48% o.d.m., corresponding to 98–100% theoretical), confirming efficient deacetylation of the hemicellulose fraction. Response surface modelling indicated that medium catalyst loadings combined with treatment temperatures of 160–170 °C and processing times of 35–60 min offer the best balance between furfural formation and the avoidance of undesired degradation reactions.
3. A key advantage of the H₃PO₄-based process is its strong selectivity toward hemicellulose hydrolysis while preserving cellulose. Across all conditions, glucan remained the major component of the LCR, and severe pretreatment scenarios still retained 38.84–40.92% o.d.m. of cellulose (94–99% of theoretical). Hemicellulose components (xylan, arabinan, galactan, mannan) were effectively removed, supporting the formation of furfural and acetic acid. Secondary degradation products (formic acid, levulinic acid, 5-HMF) remained low, indicating minimal conversion of cellulose-derived hexoses and confirming the mildness of orthophosphoric acid toward the cellulose fraction.
4. Overall, the results demonstrate that orthophosphoric acid is a promising alternative to conventional sulfuric acid catalysts for lignocellulosic biorefining. It enables high yields of C5-derived platform chemicals while retaining a structurally intact cellulose fraction suitable for subsequent conversion routes, such as 5-HMF production, nanocellulose fabrication, enzymatic hydrolysis, or bio-based material development. Given the reduced corrosiveness, simplified downstream processing, and potential for waste minimization, this approach provides a viable pathway for integrating furfural production into a broader, sustainable, and circular biorefinery framework based on birch biomass.

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